
pcDNA5/FRT-CD44-HA-TEV-Halo

 [pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-pcDNA5Rev_D10.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-CMV-F_C10.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_2-pcDNA-Rev_C10.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_5-pcDNA-Rev_D10.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B4-Halo-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B5-Halo-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F1.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F2.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F3.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F4.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F5.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F6.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-CMV-Fwd.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F1.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F2.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F3.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CMV-seq-Fwd.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-Halo-seq-Rev.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B4-Halo-seq-Rev_new.seq](#)

 [pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B4-CMV-Fwd_R.seq](#)